

Preserving Delos: 3D Documentation and Reconstruction for Cultural Heritage and Accessibility

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Abstract. The FIREFLY project aims to transform how elderly individuals engage with cultural heritage by creating a more inclusive and enjoyable experience with the help of Extended Reality (XR). Recognizing the unique needs of this demographic, FIREFLY develops a tailored user model that empowers software developers to design digital tools and applications specifically for senior citizens. These applications must be designed to be intuitive, engaging, and sensitive to the cognitive and physical challenges faced by the elderly. One of FIREFLY's most compelling case studies is the 3D mapping, documentation, and reconstruction of the Theatre and the House of Dionysus on the archaeological site of Delos, Greece. An archaeological site of sacred importance for Ancient Greece, the birthplace of Apollo and Artemis, is included in the World Heritage List and is threatened by climate change, including rising sea levels and severe weather conditions. By using advanced 3D scanning and photogrammetry, the project has captured these monuments in detail, creating digital records that preserve their beauty and historical value for future generations. Beyond preservation, these models are being used to create immersive experiences that allow elderly audiences to explore the wonders of Delos from anywhere in the world. FIREFLY's work not only safeguards cultural heritage but also ensures that it remains accessible and meaningful to everyone, especially those who might otherwise be left behind.

Keywords: Digital documentation, heritage preservation, digital archaeology, accessibility.